

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Stabilization of the Lagos-Ibadan Expressway's Ojoo-Iwo Road Section Using Geosynthetics

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Abstract

Road performance and longevity are greatly enhanced by geosynthetics. It carries out a number of functions, including reinforcement, stability, separation, fluid barrier, drainage, and filtration, to improve their use on road pavement. Geosynthetic materials were introduced to some sections of the subbase layer of the Lagos-Ibadan expressway to enhance the overall performance of the pavement. Soil samples were collected at a burrow pit at km 90 of the Lagos-Ibadan Expressway. The contractor handling the Ojoo-Iwo road segment of the expressway provided the geosynthetic materials employed in the study. The natural moisture content of the soil, sieve analysis, Atterberg limits, optimum moisture content, Maximum Dry Density (MDD), and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) were determined using standard procedures. The soil is gapped-graded, sandy-gravel, and has a plasticity index of 8%. The natural and stabilized soils have corresponding MDDs of 2040 and 1960 kg/m³. After the geosynthetic materials were added to the subbase layer, the soil sample's CBR rose from 26% to 30%.

Keywords: Geogrid; Soil Stabilization; Atterberg Limit; CBR

1. Introduction

The geotechnical performance of foundations and subbase materials is a critical aspect of construction and infrastructure development. Geosynthetics such as geotextiles, geogrids, and geomembranes, have gained significant attention for their potential to improve the stability and durability of these systems Anitha, J. (2017). The continuous decrease in availability of proper construction sites has led to the increased use of marginal ones, where the bearing capacity of the underlying deposits is very low. The conventional method is to provide deep and costly foundation on such weak deposits Jadhav et al., (2019). The necessity to develop cost effective solutions has made ground improvement a major research area. This research work identifies the geotechnical performance of foundation and subbase materials using geosynthetics such as geogrid to improve the stability, bearing capacity, and overall durability of construction projects Glen, James Barnes (2019).

Soils are heterogeneous, they vary from place to place, hence the need to carry out soil test on a building sites, to determine if the soil have the capacity to bear the load that will be imposed on it (. Construction over soft soil has always been a challenge for geotechnical engineers. Figure 1 shows the multiple functions of geosynthetics in road way applications. Hence soft soils are difficult to build embankments on due to their low shear strength, poor compressibility, and low bearing capacity. If not managed properly, weak subsoil can cause significant issues. Geosynthetics are synthetic materials used in civil engineering and construction projects to enhance the performance and durability of geotechnical and environmental structures Shashank and Ajit (2021). They serve various functions and find applications in a wide range of projects.

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Figure 3 Map of Lagos-Ibadan, Ojoo Expressway Road.

2.1. Natural Moisture Content

The natural moisture content was carried out in accordance with BS 1377 (1990) Part 2. The soil sample from the burrow pit was weigh using a weighing balance to determine its initial weight and labelled W1, after oven dried of the soil sample, it was weighed then labelled W2. Hence, $NMC = \frac{W1 - W2}{W2} \times 100$

Where W1 is initial weight of the soil sample and W2 is dry weight of the soil sample. The moisture content of the soil samples show in the table 1 below.

Table 1 Natural Moisture Content of soil sample

	%	% 15.1%
Tare n	6	1
Wet weight + tare	29.40	26.60
Dry weight + tare	27.50	24.90
Weight of tare	14.50	14.00
Wet weight	14.90	12.60
Dry weight	13.00	10.90
Moisture content	14.62	15.60

2.2. Sieve Analysis

Dried soil sample was weighed and poured inside set of sieves with different mesh sizes, placed the soil sample on the top sieve which was shaken gently for 5-10 minutes to separate the particles. The process was repeated for each sieve, working down to the smallest mesh size. The soil particles fraction retained on the sieve was collected and weighed. Hence, the result in figure 4 shows the percentage of soil particles passing through 200 was 9.8% and the result of

particle size distribution curve shows the soil sample gapped graded and table 2 shows the soil grains distribution/sieve analysis result.

Table 2 Soil Grains Distribution/Sieve Analysis Result

Sieve No.	Sieve Diameter	Sieve Wt (g)	Sieve Wt+Soil	Wt retained (g)	%Wt retained	Cum. % retained	wt	% Passing
4"	100.000			0				100
3 1/2"	90.000			0				100
3"	75.000			0				100
2 1/2"	63.000			0				100
2"	50.000			0				100
1 1/2"	37.500			0				100
1"	25.000			0				100
3/4"	19.000			0				100
3/8"	9.500			0				100
4	4.750	527.5	530.8	3.3	3.3	3.3		96.7
10	2.000	571.4	591.7	20.3	20.3	23.6		76.4
	1.180	488.3	515.2	26.9	26.9	50.5		49.5
40	0.425	450.7	468.6	17.9	17.9	68.4		31.6
70	0.212	415.9	426.2	10.3	10.3	78.7		21.3
140	0.150	407.2	412	4.8	4.8	83.5		16.5
200	0.075	409.7	416.4	6.7	6.7	90.2		9.8
	<0.075			9.8	9.8	passing n.200 sieve		
Sum (g)				90.2				
Initial Weight (g)				100				

Figure 4 Percentage passing (%) against Particle size (mm)

2.3. Atterberg Limit

The Atterberg limit test was carried out on the soil samples so as to determine its plastic and liquid limit. The results in table 3 below show that the plastic and liquid limit were 35.14% and 44.16% respectively. The Liquid Limit adopted Casagrande technique while the Plasticity Index chart result showed the soil sample has low plasticity, according to Unified Soil Classification System. **Figure 5 shows the liquid limit, where soil shifts from liquid to plastic behavior under impact while figure 6 indicates how the soil behaves under varying moisture conditions.**

Table 3 Results of Liquid/Plastic Limit Test on Soil Sample

Liquid/Plastic Limit Test	L.L	L.L	P.L	P.L
Wet weight +tare (g) at 20.10	25.7	25.8	29.9	20.4
Wet weight +tare (g) at 19.10	22.3	22.4	25.1	19.1
Wet weight +tare (g) at 16.20	14.1	14.7	14.7	15.4
Wet weight +tare (g) at 3.90	11.6	11.1	15.2	5
Dry weight (g)	8.2	7.7	10.4	3.7
Moisture content %	41.46	44.16	46.15	35.14
No. of blows	34	25	14	7

Figure 5 Moisture Content (%) against Number of Blows (mm)

Figure 6 Plasticity Chart of plasticity (%) against liquid limit (%)

2.4. Compaction Test

Compaction test was carried out to determine the maximum dry density and optimum moisture content (Mdd and Omc) respectively. Soil sample was weighed mixed with water to create a uniform paste, filled into the mould in five layers and 25blow per later to achieve maximum compaction of the soil. The sample was weighed again and record of the result was taken. The process was repeated for both samples with geogrid and without geogrid. The result of the MDD and OMC of sample with geogrid were 1960 kg/m³ **Figure 8** Dry Density (kg/m³) against Moisture Content (%) and 11.8% while the samples without geogrid are 2040 kg/m³ and 11% respectively. sample as shown in Figure 7 graph of dry density (kg/m³) against moisture content (%).

Figure 7 Graph of dry density (kg/m³) against moisture content (%)

Figure 8 Dry Density (kg/m³) against Moisture Content (%)

2.5. California Bearing Ratio CBR

The CBR test was carried out in accordance with ASTM D698, used to determine the strength of the subgrade of a road. A mould is filled with soil sample compacted with rammer of 55blows in three layers before taken to the CBR machine to determine the value. The results of the CBR value of sample without geogrid was 26% as shown in figure 9 below while CBR value of sample with geogrid was 29.9% which was approximated to 30% as shown in figure 10 below which is the standard in accordance with Federal Ministry of Work and Housing, Abuja, General Specification for Roads and Bridges in Nigeria.

Figure 9 Load (N) against Penetration (mm) (without geotextile)

Figure 10 Graph of Load (N) against Penetration (mm) (With geotextile)

3. Conclusion

The integration of geogrid increased the bearing capacity of soil sample, the sample without geogrid maximum dry density and optimum moisture content was 1960kg/m³ and 11.8% while sample with geogrid maximum dry density and optimum moisture content was 2040kg/m³ and 11% respectively. The result of CBR value of sample without geogrid was 26% while CBR value of sample with geogrid increased to 29.9% approximated to 30% which is the

standard in accordance with Federal Ministry of Work and Housing, Abuja, General Specification for Road and Bridges in Nigeria.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors, Muslihudeen Olayinka Ibrahim, Folake Olubunmi. Akintayo and Damilare Emmanuel Hassan thereby disclosed that there is no conflict of interest during the research work. All experiment undergone were done under professional scrutiny

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